

A REVIEW ON STATUS OF POLLUTION IN UTTARAKHAND

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Abstract

In Himalaya, the increased levels of urban air pollution are a major environmental problem. Pollution has become a great topic of debate at all levels in Uttarakhand and especially the air pollution because of the enhanced anthropogenic activities. Air pollution is a serious public health problem in most of the cities in Uttarakhand. The release of air pollutants in atmosphere is the direct effect of industrialisation and urbanization which are essential to meet the growing demands to the increasing population. Such activities cannot be stopped as they are directly related to the development of the society. The major anthropogenic sources of air pollutants are industrial emissions, domestic fuel burning, emissions from power plants and transportation activities. Apart from this, river Ganga is subjected to multiple uses for community water supply, irrigation, bathing, and disposal of sewage and industrial effluents. According to WHO organization, about 80% of all the diseases in human beings are caused by water. Water pollution is also a subject of concern in Uttarakhand nowadays. Noise is one of the constituents of overall environmental pollution. It has been established that excessive noise is not only adversely affecting the health of human beings but is also a health hazard to all living beings. In Uttarakhand also, noise pollution can be correlated with different cultural and spiritual events like Kumbh etc. This review collaborates different studies on three different types of pollutions hovering the Uttarakhand state and their impacts on its inhabitants.

Key words: Air pollution; Anthropogenic; Ganga; Noise pollution; Uttarakhand; Water pollution.